

STRUCTURAL DESIGN THEORY

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Abstract — *Architects and civil engineers as ‘civilization engineers’ are responsible together for the qualified design of our constructed environment. Their valuable work and inputs for our civilization affects essentially our civilized society and the quality of our life. This paper deals with an innovative reflection about university structural design theory for architects and civil engineers. Based on the Klagenfurt School of Engineering Pedagogy a practicable solution for teaching within a Bachelor-, Master- and PhD-System about structural design in the future of common education of architects and civil engineers at Universities of Technology is presented.*

Key words — *Architecture, civilization engineers, structural design, sustainability.*

GENESIS OF STRUCTURAL DESIGN THEORY

The authors Michael Olipitz and Josef Skumautz were new members of the scientific staff at the Vienna University of Technology and at the Graz University of Technology as they attended together voluntarily in September 1996 a basic course about engineering education (‘Easy Teaching of Engineering Knowledge’) at the Klagenfurt Alpen-Adria-University in Carinthia (Austria) under the academic leadership of Adolf Melezinek. The Klagenfurt School of Engineering Pedagogy accompanied the academic professional work of both civil engineers in the field of university teaching, based on their own experiences in scientifically and practical work [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8]. The authors are rooted in the tradition of the Faculty of Civil Engineering at the Graz University of Technology. In their interest in Civil Engineering Pedagogy they are following the way and example of the former Dean of this Faculty and scientist of outstanding merit, the valued teacher for hydraulic and sanitary engineering Ernst P. Nemecek. The presentation is based on that background (development) and is a derivation of optimized thoughts and requirements for the qualitative increased design, realization and implementation of the university structural design theory in the future education of architects and civil engineers at an University of Technology.

Architects and civil engineers as ‘civilization engineers’ - the term ‘civilization engineer’ was first time public stated by the new ASCE president Mr. W. Klotz on his inaugural acceptance speech 2008 - are responsible for the design of our constructed environment in the sense of a constructive critically degree of civilization in civil engineering [3]. In time of

crises like now (based on a lack of ethic in our economy and financial market - and we should not forget the problems based on the change in climate), the building and construction industry have an important position like a ‘prime mover’. We need for fresh impetus and positive repercussions the readiness for innovation within the building industry. The capability of innovation of the universities as research institutions always based on the established quality in research and teaching completes these positive efforts in the right direction. Therefore an absolutely need of sufficient financial resources are in the responsibility of each democratic state. At the same time very important are qualified teachers listening to the voice of reason and following their heart. These teachers with an excellent engineering pedagogy background are really qualified to serve as a shining example for the students. Because these teachers have only a short time period at one's disposal to give the students at the universities all necessary professional skills, stable values and virtue for their (working) life [6]. Comparable meanings were stated by Höfele, Domschke and Fritsch at the IGIP Symposia in 1999 at the Istanbul University of Technology (ITU) within the IGIP WG ‘People and Technology’). From an economic and social point of view each university and their responsible parties will still face this challenge in the future.

Since Vitruv structural design was always influenced by the same parameters (lat.: ‘venustas’, ‘firmitas’, ‘utilitas’): Aesthetics, durability and use (Fig. 1). Today they are combined in teamwork of civil engineers and architects. The examination of construction engineering, maintenance, repair, conservation and reconditioning, industrial construction, construction and design of buildings and bridge construction characterize their work. All useful aspects of ecology, economy and sociology determine the permanent sustainable and integral planning procedures. Also the necessary help of building material theory, construction physics, building chemistry, ground and hydraulic engineering shows the immanent interdisciplinary character of structural design and structural design theory. The future main emphasis in teaching structural design as a practical subject with a strong orientation to constructing buildings leads to the following concrete proposals. As a proposal and strategy the total content of structural design theory (100%) for ‘civilization engineers’ should be qualified divided into Bachelor System (35%), Master System (55%) and PhD System (9%). 1% stands for the challenges in the future (reserve position). The defined final structure of an university curricula for structural

design theory can follow this proposed fundamental and standard strategy.

BACHELOR SYSTEM

The students in the first year should become familiar with the characteristic of structural design (primarily the creativity potential of civil engineers) and need therefore sufficient knowledge in mathematics, geometry and physics (mechanics, static) at the beginning of the second term. Important for the curricula in the Bachelor System (35%) are the basics of building constructions, the basics of structural design (principles of constructions based on practicality, technology, production, comprehensive construction service and economic aspects) and the history of structural design. All subjects are supported by exercises ('practice makes perfect') which enables an interdisciplinary working relationship between different institutes of the Faculty of Civil Engineering. The Bachelor System divided into three parts leads to a third for the theory lectures, the exercises consists of two-third. The intention and aim is to show an overview and to get an 'idea' of structural design. It is necessary and important to know how to produce readable and useful technical drawings (CAD), to design constructions based on the right rules of mechanic and construction physics. Laboratory exercises support the teaching efforts and a comprehension for right structural designing. At last all students prepare a final bachelor work in structural design.

MASTER SYSTEM

In the curricula for the Master System (55%) a continuative teaching of structural building construction (specialized topics of civil engineering in building constructions) with coordinated exercises determine the consolidation of the expert knowledge. Concerning the content of structural design theory the Master System is divided into two equal parts for theory lectures and exercises. An additional special choice in the frame of high-rise constructions [1,5], industrial buildings, maintenance, conservation and repair of buildings [2] complete the specialised field in the Master Course. Very important in teaching structural design are qualitative accompanied exercises, construction physics and a permanent awareness of sustainable planning with an integral way of viewing things of the lifecycle of buildings (permanent integral life cycle awareness). For the promotion of creativeness and necessary skills to conduct team work (social competencies) between students of architecture and civil engineering an interdisciplinary teaching series makes sense [1]. Civil engineers are rather focused on mechanic aspects (design) and architects work on creativeness and design (shape). So the next generation of civilization engineers simulate by working and studying together their future practice. At last the students can prepare (alone or together) a master thesis in structural design supported by PhD candidates as teachers.

PHD SYSTEM

In Austria the 'Doctoral Schools' (e.g. PhD in Structural Design Theory 9%) were generally established. Study duration at a minimum of three years and a minimum of about 12 hours of lectures have to be consumed within the individual bilingual PhD program (minimum German and English) of the students. Furthermore PhD students should be members of a scientific team at the beginning of their study and work (experimental [2,7,8] or theoretical research, planning and physical calculations [5]). In the future the main emphasis should be laid on research in specialised fields of structural design like:

- New and recyclable building materials as useful substitution products in the maintenance, conservation and repair of buildings and in hybrid methods of building in the future. [2,4]
- Development of new structural elements under use of new building materials and further developments in facade technology. [1,2,5]
- Development of construction systems in direction of innovative future methods of building (e.g. industrial production of prefabricated construction elements and modern construction methods) motivated by permanent sustainable and integral planning procedures (permanent integral life cycle awareness). [3,4]

Professors as 'managers' and head of university research institutions [9] should additional provide from a pedagogical point of view sufficient energy laid in leading the PhD students to conduct their scientific work and in extra education of structural design theory if possible and necessary (practicable team work). It is a promotion and support of the next generation of scientific personnel (team of civil engineers and architects) in the field of structural design. The PhD work influences mainly the Master and also the Bachelor work and content of the structural design lectures and exercises. The PhD students working as scientific staff under the supervision of the professors support the master students carrying out their master thesis and final bachelor work.

FUTURE PROSPECTS

An important figure in the applied university research in the field of structural design is working with and in interdisciplinary teams inside and outside of the university. Great attention is given to the interface between the open-minded construction industry, the economy and the university. As an aim and result of it the preparation and editing of complex topics for the practicable application should be the top maxim [2, 5].

The permanent connection between the results of research work, practical work and the qualified engineer pedagogically based design of teaching (Fig. 2)

FIGURE 1
DIMENSIONS OF STRUCTURAL DESIGN THEORY EMBEDDED IN A WIDE RANGE OF SUBJECTS

FIGURE 2
TEACHING OF STRUCTURAL DESIGN THEORY AS FUNCTION OF RESEARCH AND PRACTICAL EXPERIENCE

will guarantee a high level in a specialized field of structural design theory for architects and civil engineers at an University of Technology [9].

To build up and to maintain a permanent network between universities, technical schools and the interested building economy a permanent flow of information is necessary. It is important to conduct every 3 years (as usefully interval) a professional (practical and scientific) congress in the field of structural design to enable an exchange of expertise and practical experiences (win-win strategy). An internet platform and foundation of E-Learning courses combined with established university courses by using the Internet (e.g. Web 2.0, Homepages, Instant Messenger, Blogs - technical possibilities for bidirectional communication), supplemented by writing clear comprehensible E-Books and lecture notes (electronic and hard copy versions) for students and the practice. Writing scientific and practical papers, to conduct study and field trips to building sites and to finished projects with the students are useful supports. To keep in contact with the R&D cells, branches and divisions of the building industry and consultant offices and working in teams designing national and international standards - these possible solutions as ambitious examples will guarantee a viable plan to drive the cycle shown in Figure 2.

This new approach is a challenge.

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